

APPLICATION OF INFRARED IMAGING TO REVEAL HIDDEN DEFECTS IN CFRP LAMINATES

Janice Dulieu-Barton, Rafeal Ruiz-Iglesias, Emily Leung and Riccardo Cappello

*Janice.barton@bristol.ac.uk

Bristol Composites Institute, School of Civil, Aerospace, and Design Engineering,
University of Bristol, UK

Challenges in substructural scale testing

Complex geometry

Large size

Challenging measurement space

Multi-camera set-up

FE integration

Composite/multi-material

Multi-axial test

Motivation: next generation testing pyramids

- Design & certification will increasingly rely on integrated *physical* and *virtual* testing
- Requirement for *data fusion/correlation* techniques to efficiently bridge the gap
- **Multi-camera, full-field imaging** can unlock the potential of integrated testing & modelling at subcomponent scale

DIC

IR, TSA

Thermoelastic stress analysis (TSA)

- TSA relies on the measurement of a small temperature change from a specimen subject to cyclic loading:

$$\Delta T = -T_o \frac{1}{\rho \cdot c_p} (\alpha_1 \Delta \sigma_1 + \alpha_2 \Delta \sigma_2)$$

- Assumption is temperature change occurs under adiabatic conditions
- In CFRP laminates heat conduction occurs as a result of the degree of anisotropy (thermal and mechanical) and high thermal conductivity
- Increasing the strain rate (loading frequency) reduces thermal diffusion but is limited in large structural testing and high loading rate induce viscoelastic heating

Heat transfer in CFRP laminates

Composites: Part A 149 (2021) 106515

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Composites Part A

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/compositesa

On the source of the thermoelastic response from orthotropic fibre reinforced composite laminates

Irene Jiménez-Fortunato^{a,b,*}, Daniel J. Bull^a, Ole T. Thomsen^b, Janice M. Dulieu-Barton^b

^a School of Engineering, University of Southampton, UK

^b Bristol Composites Institute, University of Bristol, UK

What can be done to use TSA effectively in CFRP structures

Numerical model of TSA in CFRP

Cappello, R., Pitarresi, G., Catalanotti, G.: Thermoelastic Stress Analysis for composite laminates: A numerical investigation. Compos Sci Technol. 241, 110103 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COMPSCITECH.2023.110103>

Coupled temperature-displacement analysis (Abaqus):

- Sinusoidal displacement boundary conditions.
- Inclusion of a surface resin-rich layer (RRL).
- Conduction between plies.
- Inclusion of surface paint layer

Test specimens and loading

Layup	Loading scenario	FPF
$[0,90]_{3S}$	Tension Loading	541 MPa

Load Ramp → Induce damage progressively (in tension)
 Cyclic Loading → TSA and LIDIC (Inspection)

Damaged Laminates (59% of the UTS)

CFRP [90,0]_{3S}

CFRP [0,90]_{3S}

CFRP [0,45,-45,0,0,0]_{3S}

CFRP [0,0,0,45,-45,0]_{3S}

Full-field data fusion to identify subsurface damage

Methodology 1 (M1): $(\Delta T/T_0)_{\text{TSA Low frequency}} - (\Delta T_{\text{SP}}/T_0)_{\text{DIC}}$

$[0,90]_{3S}$

- After FPF \rightarrow Regions of $\uparrow \Delta T/T_0$ change
- Subsurface defects start to be visible after FPF
- More subsurface features are observed with M1
- M2 shows a decrease of the subsurface response

Methodology 2 (M2): $(\Delta T/T_0)_{\text{TSA Low frequency}} - (\Delta T/T_0)_{\text{TSA High frequency}}$

$[0,45,-45,0,0,0]_S$

- Subsurface response (± 45) is observed in M1
- M2 shows a similar subsurface $\Delta T/T_0$ to M1
- Delamination is detected using M2!

$[0,0,0,45,-45,0]_S$

- Subsurface response (± 45) is observed in M1
- Wrinkles are observed
- Delamination is again detected using M2!

Full-field imaging of sandwich structures (beams)

Side view of core/face sheet interface

Martakos G, Andreasen J, Berggreen C, Thomsen O. Experimental investigation of interfacial crack arrest in sandwich beams subjected to fatigue loading using a novel crack arresting device. *Journal of Sandwich Structures & Materials*. 2019;21(2):401-421. doi:10.1177/1099636217695057

Real sandwich structures are panels - not beams where the defect is hidden under the face sheet

Face-sheet/core debonding

Test specimens and experiments

- Face-sheet – unidirectional CFRP
- Core - PVC
- Teflon film is used to create debonded region
- Loading: $-500\text{N} \pm 400\text{ N}$
- Frequency: 1 - 11 Hz

Defects identified through face sheet

Face sheet is UD – little heat transfer

- Thermal gradient is from complex 3D stress field at the debond/core interface

Lower face sheet

2.1 Hz

10.1 Hz

Can the response be related to the damage severity at the interface?

TSA to identify delaminations

Employing low loading frequency enables identification of the subsurface defect. The heat source generated in the 90° plies aids the identification, which can be further leveraged by tuning the loading frequency to defect depth.

Progress and outlook

Showed how the non-adiabatic thermoelastic response and FFDF can be used to:

Reveal subsurface damage in

- CFRP composites
- Sandwich structures

Thermoelastic response can be modelled to help interpret non-adiabatic behaviour

Next step: apply to complex structural component